

interview transcript (Manufacture resolve issues)

Interviewer: AA

Interviewee: DA (Factory Vice president)

Interview Setting: Interview conducted in shoe factory meeting room.

The interview was conducted at 13:00 PM on Monday afternoon.

Affiliation with interviewee: Chief executive officer of shoe manufacture

(Summary draft of Interview)

Interviewer : Satisfying the needs of customers: product appearance, function, physical properties, including delivery and subsequent services.

Interviewee : Product refers to what you are selling, including all of the features, advantages and benefits that your customers can enjoy from buying your goods or services. When marketing your product, you need to think about the key features and benefits your customers want or need, including (but not limited to) styling, quality, repairs, and accessories.

the processes involved in delivering your products and services to the customer.

Having good process in place ensures that you:

repeatedly deliver the same standard of service to your customers

save time and money by increasing efficiency.

Interviewer : Compliance with laws and regulations: product material and process compliance

Requirements for safety and environmental protection regulations.

Interviewee : In my position I have now, Under a broad range of federal statutes, EPA gathers health, safety and exposure data; requires necessary testing; and controls human and environmental exposures for numerous chemical substances and mixtures. EPA regulates the production and distribution of commercial and industrial chemicals, in order to ensure that chemicals for sale and use in the United States do not harm human health or the environment.

Interviewer : Confirmation of research and development capabilities: The business department needs to confirm to the R&D department that the factory has the ability to meet customer needs

Interviewee : New product research and development

R&D and product development often go hand in hand. Rapid changes in consumer demands and emerging technologies means there's always a need to adapt. Before developing new products, you need a deep understanding of the market and the user needs. This lays the groundwork for the development of the new product. Various concepts are generated and tested at the outset. These can then be prototyped for further research and testing.

Improving existing products and processes

The continual evaluation of existing products, services and processes is also a key part of R&D. If a product, service or process is no longer profitable or adding value in a market then it risks stagnating. It could also be that technology has been developed that could facilitate improvements that may cut costs, make efficiency gains or improve safety. This can include improvements to the manufacturing and production processes of the product.

Legislative changes or shifts in user wants can also mean a product or process must change or evolve to remain viable.

Interviewer : Provide solutions: resolve issues that are not in line with expectations until the customer is satisfied.

Interviewee : When a business fails to meet customer expectations, customers do business elsewhere. Poor customer service and the perceived indifference of staff and management account for about 68% of customers who don't return to a business.

Customer complaints can alert you if your business is failing to meet customer expectations. Learn more about managing customer complaints.

Some actions you can take to improve customer service are:

investigate the areas of issue

train staff in customer service and sales skills

rotate staff so they can increase their knowledge of other areas

encourage and support teamwork

review recruitment and selection procedures.

Interviewer : Due to the active investment in raw materials, production capacity, machinery and equipment and the relationship with suppliers, the company has a leading position in material development and technology and establishes a competitive advantage.

Interviewee : That is right, it's manufacture target to follow and catch brand business plan, most of items are related to support manufacture quality and fast product necessary process. But I need have plan and time in this job now to do that though. I feel that I need to teach with this job with my team, because I need to have that link to the curriculum and the status.

Interviewer : How much time allow you to get the plan with internal team ?

Interviewee : We had quite a bit of contact with supplies. I spent quite a bit of time at the machine equipment company. I worked with a couple of material supplies companies, believe after get clear plan picture just get them to get us plan and time line, can get the whole plan to meet the target.

Interviewer: Thanks for your time.

Interviewee: You are welcome.